

GRAPHIC MEDICINE

Home About Latest Reviews Conferences MultiMedia Resources Merch

Donate to Graphic Medicine Contact

Home / Comic Reviews / Graphic Non-Fiction / Embracing the Misdiagnosis: Medical Misogyny and Geographic Labeling as a Diagnostic Alibi in Powerpaola's *Virus Tropical*

Embracing the Misdiagnosis: Medical Misogyny and Geographic Labeling as a Diagnostic Alibi in Powerpaola's *Virus Tropical*

Facebook Twitter Pinterest

Author: Powerpaola with translator from Spanish Jamie Richards

Format: Paperback

Pages: 160

Publish Date: August 2016 (Spanish original published in 2011)

Publisher: 2dcloud (Original Spanish edition: La Editorial Común, 2011)

Catalog ID: ISBN-13: 978-1937541231

Where to buy: <https://2dcloud.com/products/virus-tropical>

Author website: <https://linktr.ee/powerpaola>

Review

by [Dr. Velebita Koričančić](#), Mexico City

[Powerpaola's *Virus Tropical*](#), a landmark of Latin American women-authored graphic autobiography, follows Paola through her childhood and adolescence in Quito, Ecuador, and Cali, Colombia. After being serialized, it was first published as a complete volume by Editorial Común in Argentina in 2011, and an English translation followed in 2016. The book was adapted into an [animated film in 2017](#).

Although tropical infectious disease is not its main subject, *Virus Tropical* takes its title from a series of clinical encounters in which a pregnancy is medically misinterpreted, making this coming-of-age memoir especially relevant to graphic medicine. After undergoing a tubal ligation intended to prevent future pregnancies, Hilda begins to show signs of pregnancy, but the doctors (all male) dismiss these signs. They first describe her condition as a “tropical virus,” then revise the diagnosis to an “equatorial virus,” later calling it a “phantom pregnancy,” and finally attribute it to “air.” Their explanations show that they are unwilling to reconsider what they believe to be medically possible.

This opening episode of misdiagnosis has received considerable critical attention. [Hadatty Mora \(2023\)](#) describes it as the narrative's point of origin: Powerpaola becomes the “virus tropical,” while the clinical error acts as the “germ” from which the memoir develops. Other critics situate the work within the female *Bildungsroman* and feminist autobiographical comics, emphasizing its challenge to male-centered conventions and its framing of femininity as infectious and uncontrollable within a patriarchal framework ([Gómez Gutiérrez 2015](#); [Masarah Revuelta 2016](#); [Andrade Ecchio 2019](#)).

While the succession of inaccurate diagnoses is well established in the critical literature, and the shift in geographical terms from “tropical” to “equatorial” has been noted ([Wrobel 2021](#); [Corti 2018](#)), I focus on what this geographic correction implies: **why does one doctor replace ‘tropical’ with ‘equatorial,’ as though greater geographic precision could repair diagnostic failure?** This doctor does not even reconsider the earlier premise or treat pregnancy as a possibility. He simply corrects geography. For him, “tropical” is apparently too broad, while “equatorial” sounds more exact. **The diagnosis moves closer to Hilda's geographical location but no closer to her bodily condition. Latitude substitutes for clinical observation.**

Repeated close-ups of Hilda's rounded abdomen establish the pregnancy as a graphic fact before the doctors try to name it. The gutters then mark abrupt shifts from one diagnosis to the next. In the “equatorial virus” panel, the doctor's profile dominates the foreground while Hilda peeks behind him, with her exposed belly. **The framing gives him authority while preserving the material evidence his words ignore.** The sequence ends with Hilda lying at the center of a panel as disembodied speech balloons crowd around her. The diagnoses multiply, but her body is still there, still pregnant.

Despite these shifting explanations, the scene cannot be reduced to a binary opposition between bodily knowledge, on the one hand, and medicine's claim to truth, on the other. Hilda herself doubts that she can be pregnant. Once the doctors determine that pregnancy is “impossible,” every sign of it must be explained away and reinterpreted as something else.

I introduce “**diagnostic alibi**” to name this operation. Geographic labeling draws attention away from the possibility that the earlier procedure failed and protects the belief that Hilda cannot be pregnant. Instead of reconsidering that assumption, the doctors recode the pregnancy as a viral disease. The labels change, but they do not return to the proof before them.

The labels “**tropical**” and “**equatorial**” **resonate with the history of Tropical Medicine**, in which diseases were classified through their presumed relationship to hot and humid geographic regions ([History of Science in Latin America and the Caribbean n.d.](#)). The scene can be read as a -whether inadvertent or not- parody of this for clinical reassessment. This is especially relevant to Graphic Medicine because the scene shows how doctors interpret symptoms through a cultural lens, according to what they already believe to be possible. Cultural assumptions shape what medicine believes it sees.

Medical misogyny here is more than a few male doctors being wrong about a pregnancy. Each botched explanation is embedded in a patriarchal structure that is so eager to preserve the doctors' authority while assigning less weight to Hilda's bodily evidence. The diagnoses fail, but the medical authority to diagnose is not seriously questioned. The irony is clear: the supposed “virus” is already inside the body that the doctors cannot read with the daughter who will eventually draw and narrate these clinical encounters.

To reclaim the misnamings is to appropriate the medicalized language for ironic purposes. It is to re-authorization the very terms by which her mother's experience was dismissed. In the consultation, “virus tropical” turns her geography into an etiology. In Powerpaola's retelling, what begins as a diagnostic alibi becomes evidence of how the maternal body was misread and pathologized. **By drawing the encounter, Powerpaola incorporates the medical error into the story of her own beginning. An embrace for the misdiagnosis.**

References

- Andrade Ecchio, Claudia. 2019. “Narrativa visual producida por mujeres en Latinoamérica: El autocómic como espacio de cuestionamiento y denuncia.” *Universum* 34 (2): 17–40. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0718-23762019000200017>.
- Corti, Agustín. 2018. “Extrañamiento cultural y lingüístico en *Virus tropical*.” *Quo Vadis, Romania? Zeitschrift für eine aktuelle Romanistik*, nos. 51–52: 6–23. <https://quovadisromania.univie.ac.at/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/QVR-51-52.pdf>.
- Gómez Gutiérrez, Felipe. 2015. “*Virus tropical*: Presencia y relevancia del personaje autobiográfico femenino en la novela gráfica colombiana.” *Iberoamericana* 15 (57): 85–102. <https://doi.org/10.18441/ibam.15.2015.57.85-102>.
- Hadatty Mora, Yanna. 2023. “Cinco fanzineras para el presente milenio.” In *Narrativas gráficas hispanoamericanas del siglo XXI: Una aproximación*, 10–21. Mexico City: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. <https://www.cuadernoscatredras.unam.mx/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/P-280-Cuadernos-Catedras-010-Carlos-Fuentes-05.pdf>.
- History of Science in Latin America and the Caribbean. n.d. “Tropical Medicine (1860–1940).” University of New Hampshire. Accessed June 21, 2026. <https://sites.usnh.edu/hoslac/tropical-medicine-1860-1940/>.
- Masarah Revuelta, Elena. 2016. “Lecturas feministas en el cómic autobiográfico contemporáneo.” *Filanderas: Revista Interdisciplinar de Estudios Feministas*, no. 1: 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.26754/ojs.filanderas/fil.201611507>.
- Powerpaola. 2016. *Virus Tropical*. Translated by Jamie Richards. Minneapolis: 2dcloud. Originally published 2011. <https://2dcloud.com/products/virus-tropical>.
- Wrobel, Jasmin. 2021. “Körper/Blicke und Selbst(be)zeichnungen bei Pagu, Laerte und Powerpaola.” *Closure: Kieler e-Journal für Comicforschung*, no. 7.5: 79–96. https://www.closure.uni-kiel.de/data/img/closure7.5/pdf/closure7.5_wrobel.pdf.

Dr. Velebita Koričančić (ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2941-1471>) is a Croatian professor-researcher, born in Zagreb and based in Mexico City. She holds a Master's degree in Latin American Studies, *cum laude*, from the University of Salamanca, Spain, and a PhD in Comparative Literature, with honors, from the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM). She is an Assistant Professor at Anahuac Mexico University's School of Communication and an Adjunct Professor in the Department of Latin American Studies at UNAM's School of Philosophy and Letters. She is also a Candidate-level member of Mexico's National System of Researchers and a literary translator.

Search this site...

Subscribe to the Graphic Medicine Newsletter

Join our email list to keep up with the latest Graphic Medicine news!

Enter email address ...

Sign Up

Syllabus Repository

NEW! Click on the image below to explore graphic medicine syllabi for undergraduate, graduate, and health professional courses.

